

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTION WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION. PART IX. THE PHOTOCHEMICAL OXIDATION OF ALCOHOL AND GLUCOSE BY IODINE IN ACID MEDIUM WITH TUNGSTIC ACID SOL AS PHOTSENSITISER.

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In previous papers, the kinetics of photochemical reduction of some sensitive colloidal solutions have been described. In the present paper are described the results obtained with the same colloidal solutions acting as photosensitisers of oxidation-reduction processes.

The mechanism of reaction is complicated by the fact that the incident radiation is absorbed not only by the photosensitising colloid, but also by the oxidant molecules. These latter, however, have been found to be incapable of effecting oxidation when illuminated alone in the presence of reductant. It is to be concluded, therefore, that only that part of the radiation, which is absorbed by the photosensitive colloidal material, is effective in bringing about the chemical transformation which we have observed.

The fraction of the total light absorbed by the sensitising colloid has been calculated by the approximate formula for the extinction of light by mixtures which is expressed by the equation

$$I_{\text{abs}} \text{ by A} = I_{\text{incident}} \left(1 - e^{-\epsilon_1 C_1 d_1 - \epsilon_2 C_2 d_1} \right) \times \frac{\epsilon_1 C_1}{\epsilon_1 C_1 + \epsilon_2 C_2} \quad \dots \text{ (A)}$$

The above equation gives the amount of light absorbed by A when mixed with B, the extinction coefficients and concentrations of A and B being, ϵ_1 , C_1 and ϵ_2 , C_2 respectively.

The influence of the nature of polarisation of the exciting radiations on the photosensitised oxidations was also studied.

This paper embodies our observations on the photo-oxidation of alcohol and glucose by iodine in acid medium using tungstic acid sol as photosensitiser.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The experimental arrangement and procedure were exactly the same as in the previous papers. Care was taken to prevent the escape of iodine by volatilisation during the experiment by using a well stoppered reaction vessel. The pipetting of reaction mixture was done as quickly as possible. The blank experiments recorded no loss of iodine during this operation. Iodine was estimated by titration as usual with thiosulphate.

There was no reaction when a mixture of iodine solution, hydrochloric acid and a reductant was exposed to ultraviolet rays (366 $\mu\mu$ and 333 $\mu\mu$). Also a mixture of iodine solution, tungstic acid sol and a reductant does not react when kept in the dark for 10 hours. The reactions had no induction period except in the case when glucose was used as reductant.

$K_0 = \frac{dx}{dt}$ in the following tables has been expressed as no. of g. mols. transformed per c.c. per sec.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Iodine.

TABLE I(a).

Alcohol = 4.35M. HCl = 0.063N. Sodium tungstate = 0.021M. Temp. = 33°. I_{abs} (Intensity of radiation absorbed by the reaction mixture in ergs per sq. cm. per sec.) = 1500. d (thickness of the reaction cell) = 1 cm. γ = Quantum efficiency. Mol. ext. coeff. for sodium = 650. Mol ext. coeff. for tungstic acid sol = 556 (*vide infra* Table V).

Conc. of I_2 .	I_{abs} by tungstic acid sol.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.	γ .	$\frac{\gamma}{K_0 / \sqrt{I_{abs}}}$ (by tungstic acid sol).
0.0218N	677	3.64	1.68	7.14×10^{10}
0.0052	1163	3.54	1.00	9.60×10^{10}
0.0017	1370	3.00	0.74	12.33×10^{10}

TABLE I(b).

Glucose = 0.05M. HCl = 0.072N. Temp = 32°. Sodium tungstate = 0.025M. $I_{abs} = 2700$. $d = 1$ cm.

Conc. of I_2 .	I_{abs} by tungstic acid sol.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.	γ .	$\frac{\gamma}{K_0 / \sqrt{I_{abs}}}$ (by tungstic acid sol).
0.046N	857	4.47	1.70	6.55×10^{10}
0.023	1301	3.89	0.98	9.26×10^{10}
0.019	1430	3.74	0.86	10.11×10^{10}
0.012	1730	3.37	0.64	12.35×10^{10}

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

It is evident from Fig. 1. that $1/C_{\text{iodine}}$ plotted against $\frac{I}{K_0/\sqrt{I_{\text{abs}}}}$ (by tungstic acid sol) gives us approximately a straight line.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Reductant.

TABLE II.

$d = 1 \text{ cm.}$

Concentration of

$I_{\text{abs.}}$	Temp.	I_2	reductant.	HCl.	tungstate.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
(a) Alcohol.						
1500	33°	0.0052N	4.35M	0.0625N	0.021M	3.54
"	"	"	3.85	"	"	3.27
"	"	"	3.38	"	"	3.01
"	"	"	3.1	"	"	2.86
(b) Glucose.						
2700	32°	0.043M	0.05	0.072	0.025	4.47
"	"	"	0.025	"	"	3.52
"	"	"	0.0125	"	"	2.68

By plotting $1/K$ against $1/C_2$ we get a straight line (vide Fig. 2).

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Acid.

TABLE III.

I _{abs} .	Temp.	Concentration of				K ₀ × 10 ¹⁰ .
		I ₂	reductant.	HCl.	tungstate.	
(a) Alcohol.						
1500	33°	0.0052N	4.35M	0.125N	0.021M	2.60
"	"	"	"	0.0625	"	3.54
"	"	"	"	0.042	"	4.06
(b) Glucose.						
2700	32°	0.043	0.05	0.072	0.025	4.47
"	"	"	"	0.046	"	5.42
"	"	"	"	0.024	"	3.84
"	"	"	"	0.018	"	3.47

The p^H of the reacting system at which the velocity was maximum in Table III was found to be 2.1.

Effect of Varying the Intensity of Radiation Absorbed.

TABLE IV.

 $d = 1$ cm.

Concentration of

I _{abs} .	Temp.	Concentration of				K ₀ × 10 ¹⁰ .
		I ₂	reductant	HCl.	tungstate.	
(a) Alcohol.						
850	33°	0.0052N	4.35M	0.0625N	0.021M	2.54
1500	"	"	"	"	"	3.54
(b) Glucose.						
1540	32°	0.043	0.05	0.072	0.025	3.21
2700	"	"	"	"	"	4.47

Velocity constant varies as the square root of the intensity of radiation absorbed.

Extinction Coefficient.—Extinction coefficient was determined with the help of a Moll thermopile and a Moll galvanometer.

TABLE V.

Substance used.					Mol. extinction coefficient.
Iodine	...	...	...	...	650
Tungstic acid sol	...	...	...	...	356

Quantum Efficiency of the Reaction.

Quantum efficiency (γ) of the reactions is given in Table I.

One typical example is given below.

In Table I (a), the intensity of absorbed radiation per sq. cm. per sec. = 1500

$$= \frac{1500 \times 366 \times 10^{-7}}{(6.55 \times 10^{-27}) \times (3 \times 10^{10}) \times (6.1 \times 10^{28})}$$

$$= 4.58 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Einstein.}$$

Of this absorbed radiation, the part absorbed by tungstic acid sol which alone is responsible for these photo-oxidations

$$= 4.58 \times 10^{-10} \times \frac{556 \times 0.021}{556 \times 0.021 + 0.021 \times 650} \text{ from eqn. ... (1)}$$

$$= 2.15 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Einstein.}$$

($\epsilon_{\text{tungstic acid sol}} = 556$; $\epsilon_{\text{iodine}} = 650$, *vide* Table V).

The zero-molecular velocity constant K_0 (expressed in terms of no. of g. mols. transformed in 1 sec. in 1 c. c.) = 3.74×10^{-10} ; $d = 1$ cm.

$$\gamma = \frac{3.74 \times 10^{-10}}{2.15 \times 10^{-10}} = 1.74$$

Effect of Varying the Temperature.

TABLE VI.

(a) With alcohol: Alcohol = 4.35M. Tungstate = 0.021M. Iodine = 0.0052N. HCl = 0.025N. $I_{\text{abs.}} = 1500$.			(b) With Glucose: Glucose = 0.05M. Tungstate = 0.025M. Iodine = 0.043N. HCl = 0.072N. $I_{\text{abs.}} = 2700$.		
Temp.	K.	Temp. coeff. K_{T+10}/K_T	Temp.	K.	Temp. coeff. K_{T+10}/K_T
28°	2.76	...	32°	4.47	...
33°	3.65	1.64	39°	5.79	1.80
38°	4.54	...	42°	8.04	...
(Calc.)			(Calc.)		

Temperature coefficient is rather high being of the order of 1.6 and 1.8, when the reductants used are alcohol and glucose respectively.

Comparison of the Effect of Various States of Polarisation of Light on the Velocity of Reaction.

TABLE VII.

Iodine = 0.0052*N*. Tungstate = 0.021*M*. Alcohol = 4.35*N*. HCl = 0.0625*N*
 $d = 1$ cm. Temp. = 33°.

State of polarisation.	I_{abs} .	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised light	310 ergs/cm. ² /sec.	1.36
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised light	310	1.05

TABLE VIII.

Tungstate = 0.025*M*. Iodine = 0.043*N*. HCl = 0.072*N*. Glucose = 0.05*M*.
 Temp. = 32°. $d = 0.5$ cm.

Nature of light used.	I_{abs}	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
Unpolarised	2700	4.47
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	570	2.05
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	570	1.74
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	360	1.63
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	360	1.37

From Tables VII and VIII, it is evident that $V_l > V_d$, the terms having Their usual significance.

The reaction has the following characteristics.

- (1) The velocity is proportional to the square root of the intensity of radiation absorbed.
- (2) The inverse of velocity plotted against the inverse of concentration of reductant is a straight line.
- (3) Temperature coefficient of the reactions is of the order of 1.8.
- (4) The velocity of reaction for the same intensity of absorbed radiation is larger for *l*-circularly polarised light than for *d*-circularly polarised light.

These characteristics of the reaction can be explained on the assumption that the radiation absorbed by the particles of tungstic acid sol is communicated to the mols of iodine adsorbed on their surface which thereby get dissociated into iodine atoms.

The mechanism of subsequent reactions is similar to that postulated by Ghosh and Purkayastha for photobromination of lactic acid (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 375, 383).

$\frac{dx}{dt}$ for reaction (v) is given by the equation

$$\left[\sqrt{K_2 \frac{I_{\text{abs (by tungstic acid sol)}}}{Nh\nu}} \right] \left[\frac{K_3 C_s^{1_2}}{K_5 C_s^x + K_3} \right] \left[K_5 C_s^x \right]$$

where $C_s^{1_2}$ = surface conc. of the iodine molecules

C_s^x = " " " " reductant "

Assuming that the surface concentration of I_2 is also given by Langmuir's equation

$$= \frac{K' C_s^{1_2}}{K'' + K''' C_s^{1_2}}$$

where C_2^0 = the bulk conc. of iodine molecules, The final equation for the velocity becomes

$$K_0 = \frac{dx}{dt} = \left[\sqrt{K_2 \frac{I_{\text{abs}} \text{ (by tungstic acid sol)}}{Nh\nu}} \right] \left[\frac{K_5 C_2^0}{K_5 C_2^0 + K_3} \right] \\ \times \left[\frac{K_6 C_2^{1_0}}{K_6 C_2^{1_0} + K_7} \right]$$

Hence in presence of excess of reductant,

$$\frac{I/K_0}{\sqrt{K_2} \times \frac{I_{\text{abs}} \text{ (by tungstic acid sol)}}{Nh\nu}} \quad \text{plotted against } 1/C \text{ iodine}$$

should give us a straight line

$$\text{i.e., } \sqrt{I_{\text{abs}} \text{ (by tungstic acid sol)}} \quad \text{plotted against } 1/C \text{ iodine}$$

should give us a straight line, the other terms being constant. This has been experimentally realised (*vide* Tables IA, IB and Fig. 1).

The velocity also varies as the square root of light absorbed by the tungstic acid sol and the reciprocal of the velocity plotted against the reciprocal of the concentration of the reductant under otherwise identical conditions gives a straight line.